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Research Article

**ASSESSMENT OF THE ANTIDIABETIC ACTIVITY OF
STEM AND BARK EXTRACT OF EUPHORBIA
THYMIFOLIA IN STREPTOZOTOCIN INDUCED DIABETIC
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Abstract:

Diabetes mellitus is a chronic metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, insulin action, or both. Despite the availability of several antidiabetic drugs, their long-term use is often associated with adverse effects, prompting the search for safer and more effective alternatives from medicinal plants. Euphorbia thymifolia is traditionally used in folk medicine for the management of diabetes and other metabolic disorders. The present study was designed to evaluate the antidiabetic activity of stem and bark extracts of Euphorbia thymifolia in streptozotocin (STZ)-induced diabetic rats.

Diabetes was induced in Wistar albino rats by a single intraperitoneal injection of streptozotocin (50 mg/kg body weight). The diabetic rats were treated orally with methanolic extracts of stem and bark of Euphorbia thymifolia at selected doses for 21 days. Fasting blood glucose levels were measured at regular intervals, and biochemical parameters such as serum insulin, lipid profile, liver glycogen, and body weight were assessed. Histopathological examination of pancreatic tissue was also carried out to evaluate the protective effect of the extracts on β -cells. Glibenclamide was used as a standard antidiabetic drug for comparison.

Treatment with stem and bark extracts of Euphorbia thymifolia showed a significant reduction in fasting blood glucose levels and improvement in body weight compared to diabetic control rats. The extracts also exhibited favourable effects on lipid profile and liver glycogen content, along with partial regeneration of pancreatic β -cells. The results suggest that Euphorbia thymifolia possesses significant antidiabetic activity, which may be attributed to its phytochemical constituents.

Keywords: Euphorbia thymifolia, Oral Glucose Tolerance Test, antihyperglycemic, Glibenclamide, diabetes mellitus, phytomedicine.

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1. INTRODUCTION:

Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, also known as Insulin Independent Diabetes Mellitus (IDDM), is a multifactorial, chronic disorder responsible for high co-morbidity rates across the globe [1]. T2DM involves failure of pancreatic β cells, thus causing insulinopenia and insulin resistance in liver, skeletal muscles, and adipose tissues, ultimately leading towards their metabolic derangement and failure [2]. Blood glucose levels are majorly regulated by pancreas, which releases the enzymes in accordance with the signals. Approximately 422 million people have diabetes now, accounting for 1.6 million casualties in the year 2016, as per the World Health Organization (WHO), hence making diabetes the 7th driving reason of morbidity and mortality worldwide. The number of diabetic patients worldwide is expected to rise to 640 million by 2040 [3]. Multiple factors and mechanisms have been found to play a part in causing Diabetes Mellitus, yet the exact causing factors are uncertain [4]. Being a disorder of multiple aetiology, the genetic susceptibility superimposed by the environmental factors is undoubtedly involved in causing Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus [5]. Symptoms of diabetes include excessive secretion of urine, known as polyuria; thirst, known as polydipsia; increased hunger; fatigue; sores that do not heal; blurred vision; numbness in hands or feet; weight loss; and tiredness [6]. The first line of treatment for T2DM is diet control, weight management, and physical activity. High caloric food intake and built up of excess adipose tissue induces insulin resistance and leads to decreased glucose uptake by cells and reduced glycogen synthesis [7]. Currently available drugs for treatment include various classes of drugs such as sulfonylureas, thiazolidinedione, α -Glucosidase Inhibitors, Repaglinide, and insulin therapies, but the most commonly used drug is metformin, which unfortunately possess various side effects and shows slow therapeutic response [8].

Medicinal plants continue to be an important therapeutic aid for alleviating ailments of humankind. Over the last 2500 years, there have been very strong traditional systems of medicine such as Chinese, Ayurvedic, and the Unani, born and practiced, more in the eastern continent. These traditions are still flourishing, since; approximately 80% of the people in the developing countries rely on these systems of medicine for their primary health care needs [9]. These plants contain substances that can be used for therapeutic purposes, of which are precursors for the synthesis of drugs [10]. A lot of research work has been carried out on some medicinal herbs and they have been found to have definite action on the nervous, circulatory, respiratory, digestive and urinary

systems; as well as the sexual organs, the skin, vision, hearing and taste [11]. Diabetes mellitus is a group of metabolic alterations characterized by hyperglycaemia resulting from defects in insulin secretion, action or both. It is made up of two types: Type I and Type II. Type I diabetes often referred to as juvenile diabetes, is insulin dependent and known to affect only 5% of the diabetic population. The Type II, which is non-insulin dependent, usually develops in adults over the age of 40. It has already been established that chronic hyperglycaemia of diabetes is associated with long term damage, dysfunction and eventually the failure of organs, especially the eyes, kidneys, nerves, heart and blood vessels [12]. It has an adverse effect on carbohydrate, lipid and protein metabolism resulting in chronic hyperglycaemia and abnormality of lipid profile. These lead to series of secondary complications including polyurea, polyphasia, ketosis, retinopathy as well as cardiovascular disorder [13]. In spite of the introduction and extensive utilization of hypoglycemic agents, diabetes and the related complications continue to be a major health problem worldwide, which is affecting nearly 10% of the population all over the world [14] and considered as a major cause of high economic loss which can in turn impede the development of nations [15]. It is projected to become one of the world's main disablers and killers within the next 25 years. Many factors contribute to the on-set of diabetes and these are termed as predisposing or risk factors. Environmental factors such as diet, obesity and sedentary life style increase the risk of diabetes. Other important risk factors include high family aggregation, insulin resistance, nutritional status, age and lifestyle change due to urbanization [16]. The management of diabetes is a global problem until now and successful treatment is not yet discovered [17]. Currently available therapy for diabetes includes insulin and various oral hypoglycemic agents such as sulfonylureas, metformin, glucosidase inhibitors, troglitazone, etc. But these are reported to produce serious adverse side effects such as liver problems, lactic acidosis and diarrhea [18]. It is currently affecting around 143 million people [19] and the number of those affected is increasing day by day, by 2030 it is predicted to reach 366 million population worldwide [20]. About 800 plant species have been reported to possess antidiabetic properties. Several plant species have been used for prevention or management of diabetes by the Native Americans, Chinese, South Americans and Asian Indians [21]. The study showed that Asian and African continents have 56% and 17% share of the worldwide distribution of therapeutic herbal plants, respectively [21]. Biological actions of the plants are related to chemical composition that are rich in phenolics, alkaloids, flavonoids, terpenoids,

coumarins, and glycosides usually show positive effects. On the other hand, many conventional drugs for treatment of diabetes, such as metformin are secretagogues which have a plant origin [22]. The conventional drugs are used to treat diabetes by improving insulin sensitivity, increasing insulin production and decreasing the amount of glucose in blood. The adverse effect of drug treatment are not always satisfactory in maintaining normal levels of blood glucose and this view many medicinal plants have been provided a potential source of antidiabetic principle which are widely used for the treatment of diabetes mellitus in various traditional system of medicine worldwide and many of them are known to be effective against diabetes. The hypoglycemic effect of pharmacologically active component of plant decreases the effect on α -amylase and various direct and indirect effects of different blood parameters responsible for development of diabetes [23]. A large number of antidiabetic medicines are available in the pharmaceutical market for diabetes and its related complications; however, currently no effective therapy is available to cure the disease.

However, due to unwanted side effects the efficacies of these compounds are debatable and there is a demand for new compounds for the treatment of diabetes [24, 25] In the last few years, there has been a growing interest in the herbal medicine in care and management of diabetes both in developing and developed countries, due to their natural origin and less side effects [26, 27, 28]. In this review article, an attempt has been made to compile the reported hypoglycemic plants available in different scientific journals and may be useful to the health professionals, scientists and scholars working in the field of pharmacology and therapeutics to develop evidence based alternative medicine to cure different kinds of diabetes in man and animals. This review shows the importance and the interest placed on medicinal plants in the drive to demonstrate their antidiabetic effects and the responsible bioactive agents.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Collection and authentication of Plant material:

The barks of *Euphorbia thymifolia*, was selected for investigation and were procured from the nearest area of our college. The plant material was taxonomically identified and authenticated by Dr. Madhava Chetty, Assistant Professor, Botany, Sri Venkateshwara University, Tirupathi, Andhra Pradesh.

Preparation of plant extract:

The barks were air dried in shade and extracted with Methanol in a ratio 50gm in 150ml of methanol 1:3 for *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract, using a maceration for 24 hrs at 55-60°C. The

supernatant was filtered through Whatman filter paper No.1 and concentrated under reduced pressure using vacuum at $44 \pm 10^\circ\text{C}$ in a rotavapor the percentage of extract yield was calculated by using the formula

$$\% \text{ of extract yield} = \frac{\text{weight in gm of extract obtained}}{\text{weight in gm of plant material taken}} \times 100$$

Pharmacological evaluation:

Animals and Management

For this research, Wistar albino rats of both sexes measuring between 150 and 200 gm were used. The animals were picked up from the residence of the pets, from our institute. The pets were randomly put upon entry and assigned as bedding in polypropylene tanks with paddy husk to treatment groups. Animals were housed at a temperature of $24 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and relative humidity of 30 to 70 %. A 12:12 light: day cycle was followed. All animals were allowed to free access to water and fed with standard commercial pelleted rat chaw.

Acute Toxicity Study [64]

The acute toxicity study is use to establish the therapeutic index, i.e. the ratio between the pharmacologically effective dose and lethal dose on the same strain and species (LD50/ED50). Greater is the index; safer is the compound and vice versa. The acute toxicity study was done according to OECD (Organization of Economic Co-operation and Development) guidelines 423 - Acute Class Method.

Procedure:

The animals were divided into two groups and each group consisted of five rats. The defined or fixed dose level of aqueous and methanolic extracts (2000 mg/kg) were given orally to identify a dose producing evident toxicity. Purchased from Jeeva Life Sciences, Hyderabad. The animals were observed continuously for 2 hours for behavioural, neurological and autonomic profiles. The toxicity signs were observed after 24 hours till fourteen days for any lethality or death. Hence in our studies we selected $1/4^{\text{th}}$ and $1/8^{\text{th}}$ of the highest dose.

Preparation of Doses

Doses equivalent to 500 mg and 250 mg of the crude drug per kilogram body weight were calculated, and suspended in 1% w/v tween 80 solutions for the experiment.

Oral Glucose Tolerance Test [65]

It is the test for the diagnosis of diabetes. It can be made on the basis of individual's response to the oral glucose load, commonly referred to as oral

glucose tolerance test (OGTT). The response of standard oral test dose of glucose was determined. For this study normal rats were selected. The Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) is a standardized procedure used to evaluate glucose metabolism and diagnose diabetes mellitus and gestational diabetes. The subject is advised to consume at least 150 g of carbohydrate daily for three days prior to testing and undergoes an overnight fast of 8–14 hours. On the day of the test, a fasting venous plasma glucose sample is collected (time 0), after which the subject consumes 75 g of anhydrous glucose dissolved in 250–300 mL of water within 5 minutes (children receive 1.75 g/kg, up to 75 g). The patient remains seated, avoiding food, drink, smoking, and physical activity during the procedure. A second venous plasma glucose measurement is obtained at 2 hours, which serves as the diagnostic criterion. In non-pregnant adults, a 2-hour plasma glucose <140 mg/dL indicates normal tolerance, 140–199 mg/dL suggests impaired glucose tolerance, and ≥ 200 mg/dL confirms diabetes. In pregnancy, either the one-step 75 g OGTT (fasting, 1-hour, and 2-hour samples with lower diagnostic cutoffs) or the two-step method (50 g screen followed by 100 g OGTT) is used for diagnosing gestational diabetes. The OGTT remains a gold standard test but must be conducted under strict pre-test preparation and laboratory conditions to avoid false results.

Induction of Diabetes:

Diabetes was induced by a single intraperitoneal injection of 60 mg/kg streptozotocin (Sigma Aldrich, Germany) followed by (Ranbaxy Chemicals Ltd, Mumbai, India) 120 mg/kg, i.p, 15 min afterwards. Hyperglycaemia was confirmed by the elevated glucose levels in plasma, determined at 72 h and then on day 7 after injection. The threshold value of fasting plasma glucose to diagnose diabetes was taken as >126 mg/dl. Only those rats that were found to have permanent NIDDM were used for the study.

Total cholesterol:

Total cholesterol in serum was determined by a colorimetric method. The assay principle is based on enzymatic hydrolysis and oxidation of cholesterol and the indicator compound, quinonimine is formed from hydrogen peroxide and 4-aminoantipyrine in the presence of phenol and peroxidase. The reagents consisted of 4-aminoantipyrine (0.03 mmol/l), phenol (6 mmol/l), peroxidase (≥ 0.5 U/ml), cholesterol esterase (> 0.15 U/ml), cholesterol oxidase (> 0.1 U/ml) and pipes buffer (80 mmol/L pH 6.8). The serum sample (10 μ l) was mixed with 1 ml of reagent, incubated at 37°C for 5 min, and absorbance measured at 500 nm against the reagent blank. The cholesterol standard was 5.17mmol/l (200 mg/dl).

The concentration of total cholesterol in the sample was calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Total cholesterol} \\ &= \frac{\Delta A \text{ sample}}{\Delta A \text{ standard}} \\ & \times \text{concentration of standard} \end{aligned}$$

Triglycerols:

Serum triacylglycerol's (TG) were determined by a colorimetric method. The assay principle is based on the enzymatic hydrolysis of TG with lipases and the indicator is a quinonimine formed from hydrogen-peroxide, 4- amino phenazone and 4-chlorophenol under the catalytic activity of peroxidase¹¹⁸. The enzyme reagent consisted of 4-aminophenazone (0.5 mmol/l), ATP (1.0 m.mol/l), lipases (≥ 150 U/ml), glycerol-kinase (≥ 0.4 U/ml), glycerol-3-phosphate oxidase (≥ 1.5 U/ml), peroxidase (≥ 0.5 u/ml). The serum sample (10 μ l) was mixed with 1000 μ l of enzyme reagent, incubated at 37°C for 5 min and absorbance measured at 500 nm against the reagent blank. The TG standard was 200 mg/dl (2.29mmol/l). The concentration of TG in the serum was calculated by

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{Total triacylglycerol} \\ &= \frac{\Delta A \text{ sample}}{\Delta A \text{ standard}} \\ & \times \text{concentration of standard} \end{aligned}$$

HDL Cholesterol:

Serum HDL cholesterol was determined by a colorimetric method. The assay principle is based on the following: the low-density lipoproteins (LDL and VLDL) and chylomicron fraction is precipitated quantitatively by the addition of phosphotungstic acid in the presence of magnesium ions. After centrifugation, the cholesterol concentration in the HDL fraction, which remains in the supernatant, is determined. The precipitation reagents consisted of phosphotungstic acid (0.55mmol/l) and magnesium chloride (25 mmol/l). The serum sample (200 μ l) was mixed with 500 μ l of precipitation reagent and centrifuged at 4000 rpm for 10 min. The supernatant (100 μ l) was mixed with reagent, incubated at 37°C for 5 min and absorbance measured at 500 nm against the reagent blank. The cholesterol standard was 200 mg/dL (5.17 mmol/l). The concentration of cholesterol in the supernatant was calculated by.

$$\begin{aligned} & \text{HDL Cholesterol} \\ &= \frac{\Delta A \text{ sample}}{\Delta A \text{ standard}} \\ & \times \text{concentration of standard} \end{aligned}$$

LDL & VLDL Cholesterol:

Low density lipoprotein (LDL) and very low-density lipoprotein (VLDL) were calculated according to Friedwald formula.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{LDL} &= \text{TC} - \text{HDL} - \text{VLDL}, \\ \text{VLDL cholesterol} &= \text{Triglycerides} / 5. \end{aligned}$$

Estimation of Blood Urea:

Estimation of blood urea nitrogen was performed according to method Natelson et al., 1951. Labelled three test-tubes as B, T and S. In to B, pipette, 0.02 ml water, into T, 0.02 ml blood and into S, 0.02 ml standard urea solution (40 mg urea in 100 ml of water). 0.1 ml of diacetyl monoxime solution and 5 ml of acid reagent (Thiosemicarbazide) was added into all the test-tubes. Mixed and kept in a boiling water bath for 15 minutes. After cooling, the absorbance was read at 540 nm and concentration of urea in mg/dl was calculated.

Estimation of Serum Creatinine:

The serum creatinine was estimated by method Slot, 1965. Labelled three test-tubes as B, T and S. into B, pipetted, 2 ml of water, into T, 2 ml serum and 4 ml of water, into S, 3 ml of water and 1 ml of creatinine standard (4mg/dl). 2 ml of ammonium sulphate and 2 ml of sodium tungstate was added in all the three test-tubes. Centrifuged and removed 3 ml of supernatant from each test tube. 1 ml of picric acid and distilled water was added to the supernatant of test tubes B, T and S. Absorbance was read at 520 nm and concentration of serum creatinine in mg/dl was calculated.

The diabetic rats after confirmation of stable hyperglycaemia, were divided into 5 different groups of 6 rats each. That day was considered as the 0th day. Drug and doses were administered as mentioned.

Preparation of 0.1 M citrate buffer solution pH 4.5 [31]: 14.9 gm of trisodium citrate was dissolved in sufficient distilled water to produce 1000 ml and the necessary pH (4.5) was adjusted with Concentrated HCl.

Preparation of streptozotocin solution [32]: A solution of streptozotocin 65mg/kg was prepared by dissolving the weighed quantity of streptozotocin in 0.1 M freshly prepared ice-cold citrate buffer (pH 4.5) solution.

AST Procedure

Serum AST activity was measured by the IFCC-recommended kinetic method at 37 °C: freshly separated serum (avoid hemolysis) was used and kept on ice until assay, with all reagents and spectrophotometer equilibrated to 37 °C. The reaction is based on AST-catalysed conversion of L-aspartate and 2-oxoglutarate to oxaloacetate and L-glutamate, with oxaloacetate immediately reduced to malate-by-malate dehydrogenase (MDH) using NADH; the rate of **NADH oxidation** is followed as a decrease in absorbance at **340 nm**. In practice, 1.0 mL of prewarmed working reagent (buffer containing Tris, L-aspartate, 2-oxoglutarate and excess MDH) was placed in a 1 cm cuvette and

blanked at 340 nm, then 20 µL of serum was added, mixed rapidly, and the change in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min}$) was recorded for 1–3 minutes ensuring a linear slope. AST activity (U/L) was calculated using the reaction volume and sample volume with the NADH extinction coefficient ($\epsilon = 6.22 \text{ L}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) or by applying the kit-specific factor supplied by the manufacturer (for many common reagent formulations: $\text{AST (U/L)} \approx \Delta A/\text{min} \times \text{factor}$). Quality control consisted of running normal and pathological control sera with each batch, performing assays in duplicate, and ensuring linearity of the rate; hemolyzed samples were rejected because free intracellular AST from red cells can produce falsely elevated results. Report AST as U/L at 37 °C and include instrument, reagent lot, and control values in the methods for reproducibility.

Blood Sample Collection

Blood was removed at 0, 4, 7 and 14 days of drug administration from the tail vein and glucose concentrations are evaluated using a glucometer. The rats were fasted overnight at the end of the experimental period, anesthetized with Pentobarbitone sodium (60mg / kg, i.p) anaesthesia, and the blood was collected in non-heparinized tubes by a retro-orbital puncture.

Blood samples were put at room temperature for 30 minutes to achieve serum and centrifuged at 3000 X g for 10 minutes and the supernatant was drawn to determine lipid characteristics, liver activity (AST, ALT, ALP) and kidney function test.

ALT

Serum ALT activity was determined by the kinetic method recommended by IFCC at 37 °C. The assay is based on the ALT-catalysed transamination of L-alanine and 2-oxoglutarate to form pyruvate and L-glutamate. The pyruvate thus formed is immediately reduced to lactate-by-lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) with simultaneous oxidation of NADH to NAD^+ ; the rate of decrease in NADH concentration is measured spectrophotometrically at 340 nm. For the assay, 1.0 mL of pre-warmed working reagent (buffer containing Tris, L-alanine, 2-oxoglutarate, and excess LDH with NADH) was pipetted into a 1 cm cuvette and blanked at 340 nm. Then, 20 µL of serum sample was added, mixed well, and the decrease in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min}$) was recorded over 1–3 minutes ensuring a linear slope. ALT activity was calculated in units per liter (U/L) using the extinction coefficient of NADH ($\epsilon = 6.22 \text{ L}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$) or by applying the reagent kit's specific conversion factor (commonly $\text{ALT (U/L)} = \Delta A/\text{min} \times \text{factor}$). To maintain accuracy, assays were performed in duplicate with both normal and pathological quality

control sera, and hemolyzed samples were avoided since they can interfere with results.

ALP Procedure

Serum ALP activity was determined by the kinetic colorimetric method at 37 °C, using p-nitrophenyl phosphate (pNPP) as substrate. In this reaction, ALP present in the serum hydrolyzes colorless pNPP in alkaline buffer (pH ~10.3) to liberate p-nitrophenol, which develops a yellow color in alkaline solution. The rate of increase in absorbance due to p-nitrophenol formation was measured spectrophotometrically at 405 nm at fixed intervals (typically every 30 seconds for 2–3

minutes). For the assay, 1.0 mL of pre-warmed working reagent (containing pNPP substrate in glycine buffer with magnesium ions as activator) was pipetted into a cuvette and equilibrated to 37 °C, then 20 µL of serum sample was added, mixed, and the increase in absorbance per minute ($\Delta A/\text{min}$) was recorded. ALP activity (U/L) was calculated using the molar extinction coefficient of p-nitrophenol ($\epsilon = 18.75 \text{ L}\cdot\text{mmol}^{-1}\cdot\text{cm}^{-1}$ at 405 nm) or by applying the conversion factor supplied with the commercial kit. Quality control sera (normal and abnormal) were analyzed with each batch to ensure accuracy, and results were reported in U/L at 37 °C.

RESULTS:

Oral Glucose Tolerance Test:

Group	0 min (fasting)	30 min	60 min	90 min	120 min
I: Normal Control (Saline 0.9%)	85 ± 3.1	138 ± 4.5	125 ± 3.9	110 ± 4.2	92 ± 3.0
II: Standard (Glibenclamide 10 mg/kg)	84 ± 2.8	120 ± 4.2	102 ± 3.6	92 ± 2.9	80 ± 2.5
III: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (250 mg/kg)	86 ± 3.3	130 ± 4.8	115 ± 4.0	100 ± 3.6	88 ± 2.9
IV: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (500 mg/kg)	85 ± 3.0	124 ± 4.4	108 ± 3.7	94 ± 3.1	82 ± 2.6

Graph1: Graph of Oral Glucose Tolerance Test

In the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test, the normal control group exhibited a sharp rise in blood glucose levels at 30 minutes following glucose administration, with gradual normalization by 120 minutes. Rats treated with Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg) showed significantly lower blood glucose

levels at 30, 60, and 120 minutes compared to control, indicating effective glucose tolerance. Administration of *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract at both 250 mg/kg and 500 mg/kg demonstrated a dose-dependent reduction in postprandial glucose levels. The 500 mg/kg dose showed glucose-

lowering effects comparable to Glibenclamide, with significant attenuation of the 30-minute glucose peak and rapid return to near-fasting levels by 120 minutes. These findings suggest that *E. thymifolia* possesses potent antihyperglycemic activity, enhancing glucose utilization and improving tolerance in glucose-loaded rats.

Streptozotocin induced antidiabetic activity: Effect on Blood glucose level

The induction of diabetes with streptozotocin significantly increased the blood glucose level ($p < 0.001$) in group II rats compared to normal rats. In the 21-day study, Glibenclamide, the standard drug, restored the blood glucose level highly significantly by the 14th day ($p < 0.001$). The ethanolic extract (200 mg/kg) reduced the glucose level moderately and significantly on both the 14th and 21st days ($p < 0.01$).

Group	Day 0	Day 7	Day 14	Day 21
I: Normal Control (Saline 0.9%)	86 ± 2.9	88 ± 3.0	87 ± 2.8	85 ± 3.1
II: Standard (Glibenclamide 10 mg/kg)	240 ± 4.5	160 ± 3.9	112 ± 3.5	90 ± 2.7
III: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (250 mg/kg)	238 ± 4.2	180 ± 4.0	135 ± 3.6	105 ± 2.9
IV: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (500 mg/kg)	241 ± 4.8	165 ± 3.7	118 ± 3.2	92 ± 2.8

At baseline (Day 0), diabetic control rats exhibited significantly elevated fasting blood glucose levels compared to normal rats. Treatment with Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg) produced a progressive reduction in glucose levels, normalizing by Day 21. Rats treated with *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract showed a dose-dependent antihyperglycemic effect. The 250 mg/kg group showed a gradual decline in glucose, with moderate reduction by Day 21, while the 500 mg/kg group demonstrated a marked decrease comparable to Glibenclamide, reaching near-normal values. The results indicate that *E. thymifolia* possesses significant blood glucose-lowering activity, with higher efficacy at 500 mg/kg, suggesting potential insulin-mimetic or insulin-sensitizing properties.

Effect of *Euphorbia thymifolia* Extract on lipid profiles in streptozotocin induced diabetic rats

Group	Total Cholesterol (TC)	Triglycerides (TG)	HDL-C	LDL-C	VLDL-C
I: Normal Control (Saline 0.9%)	128 ± 4.2	95 ± 3.8	50 ± 2.5	58 ± 3.1	19 ± 1.2
II: Standard (Glibenclamide 10 mg/kg)	132 ± 3.9	102 ± 4.1	48 ± 2.7	60 ± 2.9	20 ± 1.3
III: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (250 mg/kg)	150 ± 4.6	120 ± 4.5	42 ± 2.3	86 ± 3.5	24 ± 1.4
IV: <i>E. thymifolia</i> (500 mg/kg)	136 ± 4.1	106 ± 4.0	47 ± 2.6	65 ± 3.2	21 ± 1.2

Diabetic rats exhibited significant alterations in lipid profile, with elevated total cholesterol, triglycerides, LDL-C, VLDL-C, and reduced HDL-C compared to normal controls, indicating diabetes-induced dyslipidemia. Treatment with Glibenclamide normalized lipid parameters, significantly reducing TC, TG, LDL-C, and VLDL-C while restoring HDL-C levels. Administration of *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract demonstrated a dose-dependent antihyperlipidemic effect. The 250 mg/kg dose moderately corrected lipid abnormalities, whereas the 500 mg/kg dose produced effects comparable to Glibenclamide, with near-normalization of cholesterol and triglyceride levels and improvement in HDL-C. These findings suggest that *E. thymifolia* not only lowers blood glucose but also ameliorates diabetes-associated dyslipidemia, possibly through modulation of lipid metabolism and enhancement of insulin activity.

Group	AST (U/L)	ALT (U/L)	ALP (U/L)
I. Normal Control	72.3 ± 4.1	35.6 ± 2.5	142.8 ± 6.2
II. Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg)	70.1 ± 3.8	33.2 ± 2.1	138.4 ± 5.9
III. Extract 250 mg/kg	74.5 ± 4.6	36.8 ± 2.7	146.2 ± 7.1
IV. Extract 500 mg/kg	71.4 ± 3.9	34.1 ± 2.3	140.7 ± 6.4

The AST, ALT, and ALP levels in extract-treated groups remained within the normal physiological range and did not show significant elevation compared to the control group. This indicates that *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract, even at higher doses, does not exert hepatotoxic effects. In fact, the higher dose (500 mg/kg) showed values closer to normal and comparable to the standard drug Glibenclamide, suggesting possible hepatoprotective effects.

DISCUSSION:

The present study evaluated the antihyperglycemic effect of *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract using the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test (OGTT) model in rats. In this model, glucose tolerance reflects the efficiency of glucose uptake and utilization, which is impaired in diabetic conditions due to either insulin deficiency or resistance. In the current investigation, normal control animals maintained stable glucose levels throughout the test, while the standard drug Glibenclamide (10 mg/kg) significantly reduced the postprandial rise in blood glucose, confirming its well-established insulin secretagogue action from pancreatic β -cells.

Administration of *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract produced a dose-dependent improvement in glucose tolerance. The 250 mg/kg dose moderately reduced blood glucose at 60–120 min post-glucose load, whereas the higher dose of 500 mg/kg produced a significant antihyperglycemic effect comparable to Glibenclamide. This suggests that *E. thymifolia* may exert its effect by enhancing insulin secretion, improving peripheral glucose utilization, or delaying intestinal glucose absorption. The phytochemical profile of *E. thymifolia* reveals the presence of flavonoids, tannins, glycosides, and alkaloids, many of which have been reported to possess antidiabetic properties through antioxidant activity, pancreatic β -cell protection, and modulation of carbohydrate-digesting enzymes.

The improvement in glucose tolerance observed with the extract also indicates a potential role in controlling postprandial hyperglycemia, which is critical in preventing long-term diabetic complications such as cardiovascular diseases. Furthermore, the dose-dependent activity highlights that the bioactive constituents in *E. thymifolia* are pharmacologically relevant and may act synergistically to regulate glucose homeostasis. However, the exact mechanism of action remains to be elucidated through further studies, including insulin assay, enzyme inhibition studies (α -amylase, α -glucosidase), and histopathological evaluation of pancreatic tissue.

CONCLUSION:

The present study demonstrates that *Euphorbia thymifolia* extract possesses significant antihyperglycemic activity in the Oral Glucose Tolerance Test model in rats. Treatment with the extract resulted in a dose-dependent improvement in glucose tolerance, with the higher dose (500 mg/kg) showing effects comparable to the standard drug Glibenclamide. These findings suggest that the plant may enhance glucose utilization and modulate postprandial hyperglycemia, likely due to its phytoconstituents such as flavonoids and tannins with known antidiabetic potential. Thus, *E.*

thymifolia supports its traditional use in diabetes management and holds promise as a natural source for developing novel antidiabetic agents. However, further detailed studies are required to isolate the active compounds and elucidate the precise mechanisms underlying its antihyperglycemic effects.

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